

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF BADHIRYA W.S.R TO SENSORY NEURAL HEARING LOSS- A SINGLE CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined hearing loss as “a person who is not able to hear as well as someone with normal hearing-a hearing threshold of 25 dB or better in both ears.” Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) is a type of hearing loss or deafness in which the root cause lies in the inner ear or sensory organ (cochlea and associated structures) or the vestibulocochlear nerve (cranial nerve VIII). On the basis of symptoms, it can be correlated with *Badhirya* in ancient text. As *Badhirya* (SNHL) is caused by the vitiated *Vata Dosh* or *Vata-Kapha Dosh* obstructing the *Shabdavaha Srotas* (pathway of hearing) or *Shabdavaha Sira* (auditory nerve) or by the negligence of *Karnanada* (tinnitus), etc., and gives rise to diminished hearing or incapability of hearing. According to *Acharya Vagbhata* “*Ucchekrachatashurti*” (who can’t listen to the loud sound), he

eventually suffers from *Badhirya* (SNHL). **Aim:** To evaluate the effect of *Marsha Nasya* with *Anu Taila*, *Karnapurana* with *Bilwadi Taila* and *Sarivadi Vati* (orally) in the management of *Badhirya* (SNHL). **Materials and Methods:** The subject approached *Shalaky Tantra* OPD with complaints like decreased hearing along with trouble in understanding speech since 15 years. *Marsha Nasya* with *Anu Taila*, *Karnapurana* with *Bilwadi Taila*, and *Sarivadi Vati* (orally) were prescribed for the treatment of the mentioned complaints for 6 months. **Discussion:** “*Vata Vyadhi Chikitsa*” *Siddhant* can be implemented as the management of *Badhirya*. The disease is *Vata* and *Kapha* predominant. *Karnapurana* and *Nasya* are the most prescribed procedures in the management of *Badhirya*, and thus attempts are made to bring

about excellent results. **Results:** This case study indicates the significance of *Ayurvedic* management in *Badhirya*, which was confirmed by subjective improvement and by audiometric findings.

KEYWORDS: *Badhirya, Karnapurana, Nasya, Rasayana*, Sensory neural hearing loss.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined hearing loss as “a person who is not able to hear as well as someone with normal hearing –a hearing threshold of 25 dB or better in both ears.” Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) is a type of hearing loss or deafness in which the root cause lies in the inner ear or sensory organ (cochlea and associated structures) or the vestibulocochlear nerve (cranial nerve VIII). SNHL occurs when there is a problem in the sensory apparatus of the cochlea (sensory) or in the pathways of conduction of nerve impulses to the brain. SNHL can be peripheral and central (auditory pathway or cortex).

According to the WHO, over 5% of the world’s population, or 466 million people, have disabling hearing loss (432 million adults and 34 million children). It is estimated that by 2050, over 900 million people, or one in every 10 people, will have disabling hearing loss. Approximately one-third of people over 65 years of age are affected by disabling hearing loss.^[1] Sensory neural hearing loss is most common hearing loss in children which accounts for 85 to 90% of childhood hearing loss in India.^[2]

Management of sensorineural hearing loss involves employing strategies to support existing hearing, such as lip-reading, enhanced communication, etc., and amplification using hearing aids, cochlear implants, and other assistive devices. Hearing aids are specifically tuned to the individual hearing loss to give maximum benefit.^[3]

The Following are some tests that may be recommended for babies and children to diagnose hearing loss: Auditory brainstem response, central auditory evoked potential, Otoacoustic emissions, Middle ear muscle reflex, Tympanometry, B.E.R.A. Audiometry.^[4] *Acharya Sushruta* has mentioned 28 types of *Karna Rogas* (diseases of the ear) in *Uttara Tantra* Chapter 20, and *Badhirya* (HL) is one of them.^[5] According to *Acharya Sushruta*, vitiated *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas* reside in *Shabdhanuvaha Siras* and cause *Badhirya*.^[6] *Acharya Dalhana* states that not only *Vata Dosh* but also *Rakta, Pitta, and Kapha Doshas* get involved to cause *Badhirya*.^[7] According to *Acharya Vagbhatta*, *Vata* associated with *Kapha*

and getting increased or by neglect of *Karnanada* (Tinnitus) results in hearing only loud sounds, hearing with difficulty, and gradually leading to deafness.^[8]

Acharya Sushruta has mentioned in *Urdhvjatrugata Marmas* (supra clavicular region) that when *Aghata* (trauma) on *Vidhura Marma* occurs, it will lead to *Badhirya*.^[9] In *Ayurveda*, *Vataghna* and *Vatakaphaghna* are the treatments mentioned in context with *Badhirya*, which include *Vatashamaka Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Nasya*, *Karnapoorana*, oral administration of *Rasayana Sevana*, *Ghritapana*, and other *Vatahara* procedures.^[10]

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 17-year old middle-class Hindu girl, along with her parents, came to *Shalaky* OPD of our hospital on January 20, 2025, with complaints of decreased hearing in both ears and even trouble understanding speech. she couldn't hear from one room to another since her childhood, and she hadn't taken any allopathic treatment. So, she came here for further *Ayurvedic* management.

HISTORY OF PAST ILLNESS

The subject has no systemic illness.

FAMILY HISTORY

No any history found related to sensory neural hearing loss.

PERSONAL HISTORY

Table No. 1: personal history of the patient.

1.	Bowel	Regular, once a day
2.	Appetite	Good
3.	Micturition	5 to 6 times/day, once at night
4.	Sleep	8 hr in night and day sleep for 1 hour
5.	Diet	Mixed
6.	Pulse	72/min

PAREEKSHA

Table No. 2: Ashtavidha Pareeksha.

1.	<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Vata Pradhan Kapha Anubandha</i>
2.	<i>Mala</i>	<i>Prakruta</i>
3.	<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Prakruta</i>
4.	<i>Jihwa</i>	<i>Lipta</i>
5.	<i>Shabda</i>	<i>Prakruta</i>
6.	<i>Sparsha</i>	<i>Prakruta</i>

7.	<i>Druk</i>	<i>Aawila</i>
8.	<i>Akruti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>

Table No. 3: *Dashavidha Pareeksha.*

1.	<i>Prakriti</i>	<i>Vata-Pittaja</i>
2.	<i>Vikriti</i>	<i>Madhyabala</i>
3.	<i>Sara</i>	<i>Tavakasara</i>
4.	<i>Samhanana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
5.	<i>Satmya</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
6.	<i>Satva</i>	<i>Avara</i>
7.	<i>Ahara Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
8.	<i>Vyayama Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
9.	<i>Vaya</i>	<i>Bala</i>
10.	<i>Pramana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>

On Examination of Ear

Table No. 4: On Examination of Ear before treatment (20/01/2025).

Otosopic examination	Rt. Ear	Lt. Ear
EAC	Clear	Clear
Tympanic membrane	Intact and Mild retracted	Intact and Normal
Tunnic Fork Test Rinne's test- Weber's test-	AC>BC The sound lateralized towards right ear.	AC>BC -
Audiometry - PTA (Date-20/01/2025)	Severe mixed hearing loss	Moderately severe sensory neural hearing loss

TREATMENT

Table No. 5: Treatment advised from (22/01/2025 to 22/07/2025), follow up for 6 months at the interval of 15 days.

Date	Treatment	Medicine	Mode of administration	Duration
22/01/2025 to 22/04/2025	<i>Nasya Karma</i>	<i>Anu Taila</i>	6-6 drops each nostril for 7 days with a 3- days interval	3 months (3 sittings in 1 month).
22/01/2025 to 22/07/2025	Oral administration	<i>Sarivadi Vati</i>	1 Vati of 250 mg thrice a day with lukewarm water or milk after a meal.	6 months
		<i>Rasayan Churna</i>	3 gm of powder twice a day with <i>Madhu</i> , <i>Ghee</i> (unequal quantity)	6 months
22/01/2025 to 22/07/2025	<i>Karnapurana</i>	<i>Bilwadi Taila</i>	Approx. 24-26 drops (1ml). For 15 days with a 3-day interval	6 months (2 sittings in 1 month)

PATHYA-APATHYA (DO'S AND DON'TS)^[11,12]

The patient was advised to follow *Pathya Apathya* during the whole treatment duration.

Pathya

The patient was advised to do *Avyayama* (avoidance of exercise), *Ashirahsnana* (avoid head bath), *Brahmacharya* (celibacy), *Abhashana* (avoid excessive talking), *Shigru* (drum stick), *Mayura* (peacock), etc.

Apathya

The patient was advised to avoid *DantaKastha* (brushing teeth with a hard brush made out of tender branches), *Sirahsnaana* (head bath), *Vyayama* (heavy exercise), *Shrama* (physical exertion), *Pravata* (windstorm), and *Shitodaka* (drinking cold water), etc.

DISCUSSION

According to the *Acharyas*, *Srottendriya* originates from *Akasha Mahabhoota*. *Shabda* (sound) travels through *Vata* while in the presence of *Aakasha Mahabhuta* (space). Through *Shrottendriya Adhishthana (Karna)*, *Srottendriya* transmits the sound to *Shravana Buddhi*, which is responsible for the perception of sound. Thus, *Vata* plays an important role in normal hearing procedures. According to *Aacharya Sushruta*, vitiated *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas* reside in *Shabdhanuvaha Srotasa* or *Sira* and cause *Badhirya* (SNHL).

The “*VataVyadhi Chikitsa*”^[13] and *Rasayana Chikitsa* (rejuvenation therapy) can be implemented as the management of *Badhirya*. These principles probably help in the regeneration and repair of damaged hair cells, which have improved hearing. As *Acharyas* has mentioned, different kinds of treatments are used in the management of *Badhirya* (SNHL), like *Ghritapana*, *Rasayana Sevana*, *Nasya*, *Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Snehavirechana*, *Sirobasti*, *Karnapurana*, *Jalaukavacharana*,^[14] etc., but *Karnapurana* and *Nasya* are the most prescribed procedures in the management of *Badhirya* (SNHL).

As mentioned earlier, the signs and symptoms of hearing loss can be correlated with *Badhirya* in *Ayurveda*. *Badhirya* is due to the vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas*.^[15] *Anu Taila Nasya*^[16] scratches out the *Kapha Doshas* from *Shira* and improves the function of *Indriyas (Karnaindriya)*, thereby clearing the *Srotorodha*. *Anu Taila* was planned, which pacifies the aggravated *Vata Doshas* in the head and helps to normalize the function of the central nervous system by nourishing the nervous system and balancing the circulation of blood in the sense organs, including the ear.

Shringataka Marma in *Shira* is the junction of all sense organs like the eye, ear, nose, and tongue, and any medicine applied over this area targets the vitiated doshas related to all sense organs and helps in the nourishment of nerves connecting to these areas. *Karnapurana*^[17] is one of the treatments mentioned for all *Karnarogas*. *Karnapurana* with *Bilwadi Taila* has the *Vatashamaka* property and maintains normal hearing capacity, as quoted by *Acharya Charaka*. “*Na Karnaroga Vatothaha Nochchav Shrutihi, Na Badiryam Syannityam Karna Tarpanaat.*”^[18] *Sarivadi Vati*^[19] removes *Shrotorodha* and does *Vatanulomana* also It is the best *Rasayana Dravya* for *Shravnendriya Vikara*.

RESULTS

Before the start of the treatment on January 20, 2025, the audiometry report was done, which showed severe mixed hearing loss in the right ear and moderately severe sensory neural hearing loss in the left ear. After six months of treatment protocol, the patient got excellent results in subjective criteria. Now she can able to hear from one room to another, feeling relieved in her complaints and repeated Audiometry was done after treatment on July 29, 2025, which showed moderate sensory neural hearing loss in both ears.

Table No. 6: On Examination of Ear After Treatment (29/07/2025).

Otososcopic examination	Rt. Ear	Lt. Ear
EAC	Clear	Clear
Tympanic membrane	Intact and Normal	Intact and Normal
Tunnic Fork Test	AC>BC	
Rinne's test-	The sound lateralized towards	AC>BC
Weber's test-	right ear.	-
Audiometry -PTA (Date: 29/07/2025)	Moderate sensory neural hearing loss	Moderate sensory neural hearing loss

Figure: Audiometry (PTA) Report

Figure 1: Before treatment Audiometry.

Figure 2: After treatment Audiometry.

CONCLUSION

Congenital sensory neural hearing loss, can be considered as *Badhirya* due to vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha*. so, The “*Vata Vyadhi Chikitsa*” and “*Rasayana therapy*” can be implemented in management of *Badhirya* (SNHL). These principles probably help in the regeneration and repair of damaged hair cells, which have improved hearing. As *Anu Taila Nasya*, *Bilwadi Taila Karnapurana*, and *Sarivadi Vati* orally have provided excellent improvement in the present case. Thus, this case study indicates effective management of Ayurvedic oral medicine and procedures to treat *Badhirya* (sensory neural hearing loss).

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Home [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; [cited 2025 Aug 7]. Available from: <https://www.who.int>
2. Indian Journal of Otology. Title of the webpage [Internet]. [cited 2019 Dec 15]. Available from: <http://www.indianjotol.org/article.asp?issn=0971-7749>
3. Sensorineural hearing loss. In: Wikipedia [Internet]. 2023 Mar 10 [cited 2025 Aug 7]. Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sensorineural_hearing_loss

4. Bhattacharjee D. Hearing loss in children [Internet]. FirstCry Parenting; [cited 2025 Aug 7]. Available from: <https://parenting.firstcry.com/articles/hearing-loss-in-children>
5. Shastri KA. Sushruta Samhita of Maharsi Susruta with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika Hindi Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2013; Uttartantra 20/3–6. p.111.
6. Shastri KA. Sushruta Samhita of Maharsi Susruta with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika Hindi Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2013; Uttartantra 20/8. p.116.
7. Dalhana. Sushruta Samhita with Nibandha Sangrah Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2013; Nidana Sthana 1/83. p.269.
8. Tripathi B. Astanga Hridayam of Srimadvagbhata with Nirmala Hindi Commentary. Delhi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, 2014; Uttartantra 17/10. p.1000.
9. Shastri KA. Sushruta Samhita with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika Hindi Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2011; Sharir Sthana 6/46.
10. Acharya YT. Sushruta Samhita. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, 2008; Uttara Tantra 21/3.
11. Karnaroga Rogadhikara. Sushruta Samhita. Uttar Tantra, 1–4.
12. Shastri KA. Sushruta Samhita with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika Hindi Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2011; Uttartantra 21/38. p.130.
13. Shastri K. Sushruta Samhita Uttartantra. Karnagatarogavignaniyadhyayam 21/35. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2011; p.130.
14. Shastri KA. Sushruta Samhita with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika Hindi Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2011; Sharir Sthana 6/46.
15. Shastri K. Sushruta Samhita Uttartantra. Karnagatarogavignaniyam 20/08. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Prakashana, 2014; p.957.
16. Acharya YT, Acharya NR. Charaka Samhita. Sutrasthana 5/63–65. Varanasi: Chokhamba Surbharati Prakashan, 2000; p.41.
17. Shastri K. Sushruta Samhita Uttartantra. Karnagatarogavignaniyadhyayam 21/38. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2011; p.130.
18. Shastri KN, Chaturvedi GN. Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha. Sutra Sthana 5/84. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2009; p.128.
19. Chunekar KC. Bhavprakash Nighantu. Guduchyadi Varga 2/49. 6th ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Vidyabharti Academy, 2013; p.451.